

wasteless

Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress

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Executive Summary

As stated in the Grant agreement WASTELESS will create or become a part of a Knowledge Sharing Platform (KSP) for Food systems as part of its Clustering activities and this document, deliverable D7.1, explains the basis of the decision taken for the WASTELESS project to become a part of the Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform (SFSI Platform).

This deliverable provides (i) an overview of KSPs for Food Systems available through a basic desk study search, (ii) a deeper analysis, including technical specifications like: governance, features and exploitation of 5 selected platforms with focus on topics related to WASTELESS: food loss and waste, sustainability and innovation, taking in consideration stakeholders of the value chain, (iii) an analysis of food actors' knowledge and desires for online platforms through a google form survey and (iv) a critical review of the results presented in accordance with WASTELESS needs and objectives.

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AGRF	African Agriculture and Food Systems
CFS	Committee on World Food Security
CGIAR	Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research
CIAT	International Centre for Tropical Agriculture
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ETP	European Technology Platform
EU	European Union
EU-FLW	EU platform on Food Losses and Waste
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
F&BKP	Food and Business Knowledge Platform
F4T	Food for Transformation
FVCs	Food Value Chains
GEF	Global Environment Facility
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
IFPRI	International Food Policy Research Institute
K&I	Knowledge and Innovation
KSP(s)	Knowledge Sharing Platform (s)
MS	Member States
NFP	Netherlands Food Partnership
NGO	Non-government organizations
NPA	Non-profit associations
NPS	National Policies and Strategies
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SFS-MED	Sustainable Food System-Mediterranean
SFS	Sustainable Food Systems
SFSI	Sustainable Food System Innovation
SFVC	Sustainable Food Value Chains
SoMe	Social media
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TIP	The Indigenous Partnership
TCF	The Christensen Fund
UN	United Nations
VGFSyN	Voluntary Guidelines on Food Systems and Nutrition
WFF	World Food Forum
WFP	World Food Programme
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature

1. Introduction

The [Farm to Fork strategy](#), as the core of the EU Commission's agenda to achieve the [Sustainable Development Goals](#) (SDGs) highlights the need to redesign our food system to deliver sustainable, healthy diets for all. Food systems are heterogenous, dynamic, and very diverse and involve multiple interactions between human and natural components. [2] The broader definition of food systems given by Erikson, 2008, includes: the interactions between and within bio-geophysical and human environments, which determine (i) a set of activities, (ii) the activities themselves, from production through to consumption, (iii) the outcomes of the activities and (iv) other determinants of food security [3]. In simple and recent words found in [SRIA, ETP "Food for Life"](#) (2024) a food system is a complex network that involve various activities, processes, and individuals working together to produce, process, distribute, and consume food. Building sustainable food systems has become a predominating endeavour aiming to redirect our food systems and policies towards better-adjusted goals and improved societal welfare [2]. Reducing food loss and waste is also an integral part of the EU's 2020 Farm to Fork strategy as a key to achieving sustainability and the Commission is committed to halving per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030 (SDG Target 12.3).

Understanding how to manage food systems to achieve sustainability raises considerable challenges as all citizens and operators across value chains worldwide should act and benefit from this transition. Even if a great deal of knowledge has been generated over the last years it is often heterogenous, unstructured and not explicit enough. Furthermore, ensuring that all this knowledge is integrated, and it leads to better outcomes is a demanding task. The shift toward modern food systems should be accompanied by holistic interactions among interdependent components like information, communication, governance, cultural dynamics and transforming food politics, all with an impact on food systems' dynamics [4].

Increased digitalisation and openness of knowledge led to the development of online platforms. Since back in 2001, when the United Nations' Human Development Report [5] mentioned digital platforms as a way of sharing data, these online tools have evolved and are nowadays widely used mainly as 'open spaces' with a central position in the business models of the largest companies in the world, with potential to generate social and economic value for development [6]. Such platforms are defined as a set of digital resources—including services and content—that enable value-creating interactions between external producers and consumers [7]. Based on their principal purpose digital platforms can be food transaction platforms and innovation platforms [6]. As the name suggests, food transaction platforms have the main goal of facilitating food transactions between different actors (e.g., farmer, retailers, consumers), while innovation platforms connect and motivate multiple stakeholders around a common goal or purpose, seeking to shape new long-term visions into the transformation of food systems [8]. Nowadays, some of these platforms are not limited only to transactions and/or innovations but are complementary.

In the case of food systems, the creation and use of different online platforms can foster both individual and group knowledge within the entire food system or a particular area (e.g. food waste). An online communication and collaboration platform, one that is user-friendly with a simple interface and accessible both on a phone and on a computer, may help all stakeholders to better profit from their participation in the food supply chain [9]. If in the food system transactional online platforms (e.g. delivery, takeaway) dominate with increased popularity, especially due to the COVID-19 pandemic [10], innovation platforms also exist. Based on their structure they are either being developed by public bodies, are designed by research projects, or are driven by individual members around a particular topic of concern [11]. Even if online platforms have a high potential to change the food system, their governance arrangements and their ability to effectively bring together actors for collaborative action are two main challenges that must be considered.

In conclusion, the need of a continuous transformation of food systems is overall accepted. However, the path toward this transformation is not simple and involves all value chain actors with focus on how they benefit and interact. Online platforms can thrive positive change through free information-networked activities for innovative development.

2. Knowledge Sharing Platforms (KSPs) for Food Systems

Online platforms may help with transformation to sustainable food systems by sharing knowledge from different food sectors, between food actors and, by promoting activities and collaborations between them. The fast development of digital technologies made numerous food system platforms available, and they can be used by food chain actors. Which one should they use? This is a difficult decision and is many times based on the impact and reliability of such platforms. This section aims to reveal what KSPs for food systems are out there and what information they provide.

2.1. Methodology

A desk study was performed in November 2023 by two independent researchers using the search term “Food system (s) online platforms”. The criteria adopted was to consider any platform which provided knowledge about ‘Food Systems’ in general including any focus area. After analysing the first 60 results on Google, the analysis was stopped because the further results showed were not relevant anymore (mostly including food transactional platforms). At this point, researchers combined their results, excluded the duplicates, discussed any doubts and in the end agreed on the final list.

2.2. Results and discussion

The desk study search resulted in a list of 25 diversified KSPs, all entries are presented in Table 1, shown in alphabetical order, and all analysed by their description, governance, information provided, and main topics covered. A link to each platform, if available, was also provided for further information. Among the included KSPs the following types were found: knowledge databases (e.g., Evidence platform for agrifood systems and nutrition, Planet-based diets, Urban Food Actions Platform, SFSI Platform), project websites (e.g., Food4transformation, ReFooture), networking platforms (e.g., Food 2030 online platform), community platforms (e.g., FERMENT), summit websites (e.g., UN The Food Systems Summit), forum websites (e.g., World Food Forum), gaming platforms (e.g., Change the Game, Change the Future platform) and learning platforms (e.g., The Indigenous partnership for Agrobiodiversity and Food Sovereignty, Sustainable Food value chains knowledge platform).

Some of these KSPs are already over and continued by others, as is the case of F&BKP that was continued by NFP. Many others are still running with reduced activity as seen by the date of the latest articles published and the events announcements, for example Food Systems Change platform (latest article is from 2020 and the next event coming is 29/11/2023). These platforms are still valuable because they store the knowledge produced at that time. The reason for this lack of activity may be that the projects funding them ended. To ensure the sustainability of their outputs these platforms can either place all their knowledge on an active repository or be taken over by others (projects or organisations), like NFP. If the platforms are not active the probability of being shown in a search is reduced and the knowledge available on them will be lost. In contrast, there are other platforms with few updates on their knowledge but with updated news and events sections, like the FOSTER and ReFooture platforms. These are two project websites predicted to accommodate a KSP by 2027. In the case of FOSTER, the platform already exists but with no content yet, while in the case of ReFooture the platform is predicted as the Phase II of the project, and it should be now in its development phase.

Fifteen KSPs found in the desk study search focus on the food systems at worldwide level, while the others are focused on a specific area. Four in Europe (Food 2030 online platform, Food systems change, Knowledge platform FOSTER, SFSI platform), three in Africa (Africa Food Systems Forum, Food System Innovation platform-ReFooture, Resilient Food Systems), one mediterranean (SFS-MED platform), and other one that covers Latin America and Caribbean, Asia and Africa (The Alliance Bioversity – CIAT platform) which includes PlaSa Colombia platform.

Table 1. List of KSPs for food systems using the search term “Food system(s) online platforms” displayed by alphabetical order. (Publications when referred may include scientific and non-scientific publications or only one of them, check the weblinks for deeper information.)

Name (focus area)	Description (taken from the platform and adapted)	Governance	Information provided	Main topics covered
Alliance Bioversity – CIAT (Latin America and the Caribbean, Asia and Africa)	The Alliance delivers research-based solutions that harness agricultural biodiversity and sustainably transform food systems to improve people’s lives. To do so, the Alliance works with local, national and multinational partners across Latin America and the Caribbean, Asia and Africa, and with the public and private sectors. With partners, the Alliance generates evidence and mainstreams innovations in large-scale programs to create food systems and landscapes that sustain the planet, drive prosperity and nourish people in a climate crisis.	CGIAR initiative: National Policies and Strategies (NPS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stories - Events - Paths to impact - Publications & data - Tools & Innovations - Annual reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food Environment & Consumer Behaviour - Multifunctional Landscapes - Climate Action - Agrobiodiversity - Digital Inclusion - Improving Crops - Gender Inclusion
Africa Food Systems Forum (Africa)	Since 2010, the Africa Food Systems Forum has been an annual gathering held in different regions of Africa, with evolving themes. Heads of State, Ministers, business leaders, development partners, thought leaders, farmers, youth, and other stakeholders come together to focus on actionable measures and policies to drive the continental agenda forward. Over time, the Africa Food Systems Forum has expanded its scope to include a greater emphasis on food systems and integrated approaches, government engagement, reporting and accountability, and mobilizing the private sector.	AGRF-FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Annual summit - Partnerships - Publications - Podcasts - Events - News - Blog 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agribusiness deal room - Agtech & Digitalization - Food systems & nutrition - Generation in Africa - Inputs - Policy & state capability - Regional trade - Resilience & adaptation - Rural & Market development - Women in agriculture
Change the Game, Change the Future Platform (Worldwide)	The game platform “ Change the Game, Change the Future ” was introduced during a 5-day flagship event of the World Food Forum (WFF), a youth-led movement to help shape the future of food and agriculture. The online game platform mixes real-time data from over 190 countries with interactive animations that depict local cultures across the globe. Through playing the game, both policymakers and the public can learn to manage complex, real-life trade-offs while seeking a balance between economic growth, social progress and environmental protection. Beneath the game’s surface, advanced quantitative global modeling tools analyze these tradeoffs and provide synergies with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.	FAO & The Lexicon	Not applicable	Food systems
EAT (Worldwide)	EAT is a science-based global platform for food system transformation. EAT is a non-profit dedicated to transforming our global food system through sound science, impatient disruption and novel partnerships.	Stordalen Foundation, Stockholm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Events - Partners/networking - Initiatives - Publications - Weblinks - News 	Food systems

Table 1. (cont)

Name (focus area)	Description (taken from the platform and adapted)	Governance	Information provided	Main topics covered
EIT Foods (Worldwide)	EIT Food accelerates innovation to build a future-fit food system that produces healthy and sustainable food for all. The world's largest and most dynamic food innovation community which create connections right across the food system that stimulate new ideas and innovations to drive change: between startups and corporates; between food entrepreneurs and investors; between consumers and industry; between research and action; between ideas and reality; between present and future.	EU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community - Publications - Podcasts - Blog - Events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Healthier lives through Food - Net zero Food system - Reducing risk for a fair and resilient Food System
Evidence platform for agrifood systems and nutrition (Worldwide)	This platform provides evidence and tools to support governments and stakeholders in the uptake of the Voluntary Guidelines on Food Systems and Nutrition (VGFSyN) of the Committee on World Food Security (CFS). This platform was developed by FAO in collaboration with UN Nutrition, to facilitate the implementation of the 105 VGFSyN recommendations for action aiming at achieving sustainable agrifood systems, enabling healthy diets and improving nutrition. To find relevant documents for a VGFSyN recommendation, users need to select a focus area and the sub-focus area of interest and will be redirected to a page listing all relevant VGFSyN recommendations.	FAO	Focus areas	Agri-food systems and nutrition
Food and Business Knowledge platform (F&BKP) (Worldwide)	During 2013-2020, the F&BKP Knowledge Portal provided Food & Nutrition Security professionals with annotated references to knowledge and innovations in their work field. The contributions resulted in an extensive and rich knowledge base. Although new input is not added anymore, all valuable content built over the years remains available. The Knowledge Portal shared selected knowledge items in the field of Food and Nutrition Security. Over the years, the Knowledge Portal contained 24 topics, including inclusive business, consumption patterns, youth, livestock, seeds and policies, approached from a national, regional, international or global angle.	NFP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publications - Toolkits - Partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agribusiness development and trade - Sustainable agriculture - Innovations in agro-food sectors - Food security policy and governance - Consumption partners and nutrition - Cross-cutting challenges to food security
Food 2030 online platform (Europe)	The platform will be the home of two networks: the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network and the FOOD 2030 Connected Lab Network.	CLEVERFOOD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network - Publications - Toolkits - News - Events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Related to the EU projects in the network

Table 1. (cont)

Name (focus area)	Description (taken from the platform and adapted)	Governance	Information provided	Main topics covered
Food System change (Europe)	Since September 2018, this website has been offering a virtual space to all those who are committed to a sustainable food system. This is where you can obtain knowledge about current research findings and practical experiences. You can present your results, initiatives and projects. The platform thrives thanks to the volunteer contribution of others.	NAHhaft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publications - Projects - Niche innovations - Plant Europe networking 	Food systems
Food System Innovation platform-ReFooture (Africa)	Phase II (2023-2027) of REFOOTURE project, consolidate the regenerative inclusive food system development approach on the basis of a successful food system innovation platform.	REFOOTURE	Not applicable (under construction)	Food systems
Food Systems-Food4transformation (F4T) (Worldwide)	Since 2017, Food4Transformation (F4T) has been tackling SDG 2 to achieve nutrition for the world population. The website provides a collaborative communication platform for actors across the agricultural landscape to share their views, including representatives from civil society, public policy, the private sector, and research. This is a platform for the sharing of ideas and approaches for the Transformation of Agricultural and Food Systems.	F4T (civil society, science, business and politics collaboration)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Podcast - By numbers - Agri-food map - Innovation lab - Special editions - Newsletter 	Transformation of Agricultural and Food systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate - Digitalization & Innovation - Food Systems - Gender - People & perspectives - Politics - Trade & supply chains
Knowledge platform-FOSTER (Europe)	The vision of FOSTER is to build a foundation from which a new Knowledge and Innovation (K&I) governance structure for Europe's food system can emerge. This new structure is needed because the current K&I system in the European Research Area (ERA) is insufficient to address the emerging challenges of nourishing Europe in a healthy, affordable and sustainable way.	FOSTER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publications - News - Events - Academy - Future Food Systems <p><i>(Started 2023, not many data available)</i></p>	Europe's Food System <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food & Nutrition Security - Environmental sustainability - Economic and social well-being
Netherlands Food Partnership (NFP) (Worldwide)	Food & Business Knowledge Platform (F&BKP) and AgriProFocus transformed into Netherlands Food Partnership (NFP). NFP is the leading Dutch instrument that facilitates the necessary acceleration in achieving SDG2, supported by the Dutch government. NFP enables powerful collaboration between relevant Dutch organisations and international partners to achieve urgent changes that contribute to sustainable food systems and nutrition security and reach SDG2 by 2030. NFP connects to accelerate – for bigger impact.	NFP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community - Training - Initiatives - News 	Food systems

Table 1. (cont)

Name (focus area)	Description (taken from the platform and adapted)	Governance	Information provided	Main topics covered
Planet-Based Diets (Worldwide)	A science-based platform to encourage diets that are good for people and the planet. A comprehensive scientific assessment of how dietary shifts in 147 countries can bend the curve on the negative impacts of the food system, moving from exploiting to restoring nature.	WWF (panda.org)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National impacts - Actions - Policy - Science - Insights - Build your diet 	Planet-based diets
PlaSA Colombia (Colombia)	A platform to report, monitor and analyze what is happening in Colombia's food systems. This platform is an online tool that synthesizes and democratizes data and information, currently dispersed, helping in decision-making, legislation on food safety and to articulate actions from different actors. It's an easily accessible space in which anyone interested in the complex universe of the food system will find from data to narratives based on truthful, simple, and updated information to better understand dynamics, drivers, main components and trade-offs of the country's food systems.	Alliance Biodiversity – CIAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Events - Publications - Interactive guideline - Explore 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food production and financing - Distribution of livestock - Food supply - Food miles - Food mobilization - Environmental impact from food mobilization - Nutritional status of the Colombian population according to BMI - Cost and affordability of a health, nutritious and subsistence diet in Cali
Resilient Food Systems (Africa)	Integrated approach pilot committed to fostering sustainability and resilience for food security in sub-Saharan Africa, contributing to a paradigm shift in the continent's agriculture one which emphasises the importance of natural capital and ecosystem services to enhance agricultural productivity.	Global Environment Facility (GEF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge Centre - Country projects - Regional hub - News - Events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food systems - Agroforestry & reforestation - Sustainable land management - Integrated water resource management - Value chains & market access - Rural extension & capacity development - Monitoring & evaluation - Science, policy & institutions - Knowledge & learning - Gender

Table 1. (cont)

Name (focus area)	Description (taken from the platform and adapted)	Governance	Information provided	Main topics covered
SFS-MED platform (Mediterranean)	Is a multi-stakeholder initiative aimed at promoting collaborative actions for the sustainable transformation of food systems in the Mediterranean, ultimately accelerating progress on the delivery of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in the region.	One Planet Network's Sustainable Food System programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community of practice - Publications - News - Events 	Sustainable Food Systems in the Mediterranean
Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform (SFSI) (Europe)	Online environment for those interested in SFS, where individual users can browse or search many databases, and registered users can upload their own work and comment on the work of others. The Platform also offers links to free online courses on topics geared towards small and mid-sized food professionals	EU funded projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case studies - Initiatives - Innovations - Practice abstracts - Publications - Weblinks - Training courses - Community groups 	Related to the EU managing and contributors' projects
Sustainable Food value chains knowledge platform (Worldwide)	This global knowledge platform provides a user-friendly gateway to practical guidance and information on the development of Sustainable Food Value Chains (SFVC). SFVC development is a market-oriented and systems-based approach for measuring, analysing and improving the performance of food value chains (FVCs) in ways that help ensure their economic, social and environmental sustainability.	FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Library - Training and learning center - News - Events 	Sustainable Food Value Chains
TABLE (Worldwide)	TABLE is a food systems platform that sets out the evidence, assumptions and values that people bring to debates about resilient and sustainable food futures. Includes a community discussion platform (FERMENT) where everyone is welcome to ask questions, share information, and start new discussions (or join existing ones) about food sustainability.	TABLE (Universities collaboration: University of Oxford, SLU, WUR, Cornell calls, IIS-UNAM, Universidad de los Andes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Podcasts - Explainers - Publications - Blog - Research library - Themes and projects - Community FERMENT - Newsletter FOODER 	Food systems

Table 1. (cont)

Name (focus area)	Description (taken from the platform and adapted)	Governance	Information provided	Main topics covered
Technical Platform on the Measurement and Reduction of Food Loss and Waste (Worldwide)	<p>The G20 (May 2015) recommendation to reduce FLW held in Turkey, was followed by the agreement between FAO and the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) to set up the Technical Platform to measure and reduce food loss and waste. Launched in December 2015, the Technical Platform facilitates information-sharing and in-depth discussion. The platform builds on and complements existing initiatives by FAO and CGIAR (formerly the Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research) Research Program on Policies, Institutions, and Markets, which includes an initiative on measuring and reducing food loss and waste.</p>	FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community of Practice - News - Events - Publications - Multimedia - In action 	Food Loss & Food Waste
The Indigenous partnership for Agrobiodiversity and Food Sovereignty (TIP) (Worldwide)	<p>This learning platform brings together resources about indigenous food systems. All materials are categorised into six interrelated themes. Under each theme users will find Publications and guidelines (guidelines, manuals and case studies) and Talks and videos (expert talks, documentaries and videos). An intercultural approach that seeks to bridge indigenous and scientific knowledge systems for mutual learning and actions.</p>	The Christensen Fund (TCF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning platform - Indigenous stories - Partners/Networking - News 	Indigenous Food systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agrobiodiversity and agroecology - Food, nutrition and health - Land and resilience - Women and youth - Indigenous knowledge and innovation - Livelihoods
UN The Food Systems Summit (Worldwide)	<p>The 2021 Summit that launched bold new actions to deliver progress on all 17 SDGs, each of which relies to some degree on healthier, more sustainable and equitable food systems.</p>	UN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publications - Events - News - Take action - Summit dialogues 	Food Systems Summit 2021
Urban Food Actions Platform (Worldwide)	<p>This Platform provides access to a comprehensive database of resources related to urban policies and programmes, to achieve sustainable urban food systems. It covers a wide range of aspects: Governance and planning, Sustainable diets and nutrition, Social and economic equity, Food production and ecosystem management, Food supply and distribution, Food loss and waste.</p>	FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explore topics - Resources - Events - Share with us - Food For Cities network 	Urban policies and programmes
World Food Forum (Worldwide)	<p>Independent, youth-led global network of partners facilitated by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). It aims to spark a global movement that empowers young people everywhere to actively shape agrifood systems to help achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and a better food future for all.</p>	FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results reports - Events - News 	Food systems

The Alliance Bioversity – CIAT platform was found after analysing the PlaSa Colombia platform, being part of the Tools & Innovations of the first one, together with many other food system platforms. It is a food systems platform within another food system platform, one is specific for Colombia but the other includes many other platforms specific to other Latin America countries and Caribbean, Asia and Africa. PlaSa Colombia appeared in the search and Alliance Bioversity – CIAT didn't, may be due to the user's traffic which is higher in PlaSa Colombia than the general one or any other platform in there. The Alliance Bioversity – CIAT is in the view of the authors a very good example of a KSP for food systems, it specifies its content by topic (food systems) and area (Latin America and Caribbean, Asia and Africa) including as many possible KSPs, and the success of one lead to the finding of others.

The majority of existing KSPs are under the patronage of well - known organisation(s) (e.g. EIT Foods, Evidence platform for agrifood systems and nutrition), which grant them with reliability and trust. There are also KSPs built by projects (e.g. Food 2030 online platform, Food System Innovation platform-ReFooture) and in this case the management of the platform is done through the involvement of one or more organisations as partners in the respective project. There are also platforms serving different big events and managed by the organisations involved in the event itself. In the case of the SFSI Platform the governance is done through the collaboration of several EU funded projects including many actors of the food values chain. The governance of the KSPs is one of the main aspects to ensure the sustainability of knowledge available on the KSPs in a long term. In general, project platforms end or remain inactive after the end of the project while platforms governed by organisations have a longer lifetime.

2.3. Synthesis and critical view

The results here show clearly that many KSPs for Food Systems are now available and can be found in a general search. If the search is narrowed down to specific areas or terms many other KSPs would appear. All these platforms provide different information for food system actors: knowledge databases, scientific publications, training, networking, initiatives, stories, newsletters, press-releases, tools and innovations, news, latest events, and others. However, many questions rise at this point: Are this many KSPs needed? Are they useful for the food actors? Is the knowledge easy to find and to understand by all food actors? Are all these platforms reliable and trustworthy? And what would be the future? If any project, organisation and/or individual builds such platforms related to general or specific topics, how can food actors select and have the certainty that their selection is accurate? Are the networking, collaborations and partnerships being effective and successful? Maybe the intervention of EU would be necessary to give some perspectives regarding the impact of existing KSPs and to ensure food chain actors of trust and reliability.

3. Analysis of 5 selected KSPs for Food Systems

The aim of the WASTELESS project was either to develop or to be a part of a KSP. Based on the analysis previously performed, 5 platforms were selected for a deeper analysis focusing on their description, governance, target audience, features and exploitation. From the list included in Table 1 the following two active KSPs with focus on Europe, and often discussed in recent Food Systems events were selected: the Sustainable Food System Innovation (SFSI) platform and the FOOD 2030 Online platform. Another platform was selected using the same criteria but not listed in table 1, the EU-FarmBook platform. Other two platforms were selected due to their topic specificity on FLW, one from the list, the Technical Platform on the Measurement and Reduction of Food Loss and Waste, in this case with a worldwide focus, and the well-known EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste (EU-FLW) platform.

3.1. Sustainable Food System Innovation (SFSI) Platform

Description: The SFSI Platform is an online environment, in the form of a web page, where all stakeholders interested in the development of sustainable food systems can search 6 different databases or can upload their work to make it available even after the end of the project.

Governance: The platform is managed by EU projects that when finished are replaced by others. At the time this deliverable is being written, the platform is managed by 5 EU projects, while 4 others EU projects are contributing to the development of the platform.

Target at: The SFSI Platform is aimed at all food value chain stakeholders including Farmer & Cooperatives, Industry & Retail, Policy makers, Technology providers and Consumers.

Features: The SFSI Platform features beside the Home and About us pages, the Inventory page (Case studies, Initiative, Innovation, Practice abstracts, Publications, Web links), the Training page and the Community groups page. All databases include outputs from more than 13 finished or running projects available in multiple languages. The SFSI Platform aims to encourage: i) generating, sharing, discussing, and using information on food supply chain innovations; ii) publicizing successful innovative food supply initiatives; iii) access to both targeted and general training materials and e-learning about innovative food supply chains; iv) availability of public project documents and reports as well as relevant publications in any form (videos, presentations, infographics); and v) cooperation and discussion among related European and national projects and associations.

Exploitation: The SFSI Platform was launched by the SMARTCHAIN project, which ran from September 2018 through August 2021. After that the platform was rebranded by the 5 sister projects funded under the RUR6 and RUR7 H2020 call. At this time the sustainability of the SFSI Platform with all its features is and will be ensured by continually integrating new projects acting in the field of food systems willing to manage or contribute to it.

3.2. Food 2030 Online Platform

Description: The FOOD 2030 Online Platform, in the form of a webpage and network, is a common platform for all projects, partnerships, networks, living labs, communities of practice and other initiatives working on transforming the food system for the benefit of the people and the planet.

Governance: the EU funded project CLEVERFOOD has developed and manages the FOOD 2030 platform.

Target at: All projects, partnerships, networks, living labs, communities of practice and other initiatives acting in the field of food systems.

Features: The platform will be the home of two networks: the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network and the FOOD 2030 Connected Lab Network. By joining these networks members of the FOOD2030 platform will be able to: i) expand their own network and join forces with like-minded projects, ii) share successful practices and explore synergies, iii) receive targeted support and develop new competences, iv) collaborate on activities and

organize joint events, v) showcase project results and maximize impact, vi) influence policymaking and inform future EU legislation. Aside from the ‘Home’ and ‘About us’ pages, the FOOD 2030 Platform features a ‘Resources and Toolkits’ page (Stakeholder analysis, Trends in the food systems, Visioning, Visioning on the role of R&I for future proof-systems, Usability testing, Out-of-the-box thinking) as well as pages for ‘News’, ‘Events’ and ‘Contacts’.

Exploitation: The platform has been launched in 2023 by the CLEVERFOOD project which runs until December 2026.

3.3. EU- FarmBook Platform

Description: The EU-FarmBook platform is an online platform, in the form of a web page, as the place where farmers, foresters and advisors get inspired to innovate.

Governance: The platform is managed by the EU-FarmBook Horizon Europe project that is working at regional, national, and European levels to build an Online Platform gathering and sharing agriculture and forestry knowledge. It is supposed that after the end of the project the Platform will be taken over by the EC which will ensure its governance.

Target at: EU-FarmBook is the answer to real needs of farmers, foresters and advisors.

Features: The EU-FarmBook platform is an open-source interactive database including material useful for practice such as videos, user manuals, infographics and much more together. It offers an interactive, multi-lingual meeting place for agriculture and forestry communities, giving access to trustworthy knowledge objects according to findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data principles. EU-FarmBook users can interact and explore innovative ways to solve their daily challenges. The platform features the ‘About us’ page, offers ‘Support’ in the form of training sessions for users to learn how to upload materials, and offers materials on 6 topics: Forestry, Livestock, Crop farming, Economics, Environment, Society.

Exploitation: The platform was launched in late 2023 and it is managed by the EU-FarmBook project running until end of July 2029.

3.4. Technical Platform on the Measurement and Reduction of Food Loss and Waste

Description: The Technical Platform of the Measurement and Reduction of Food Loss and Waste is an online platform available on the FAO website with the aim of facilitating information sharing and in-depth discussion. The platform builds on and complements existing initiatives by FAO and CGIAR Research Program on Policies, Institutions, and Markets, which includes an initiative on measuring and reducing food loss and waste.

Governance: The platform is built on the FAO website at the initiative of the G20 agriculture ministers by the agreement between FAO and the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).

Target at: The target groups are not specifically mentioned but the Technical platform is open to all interested stakeholders worldwide.

Features: The Technical platform includes sections specifically on: Food loss, Food waste, Community of practice (CoP), News and Events, Resources and In action. The CoP is one of the major outcomes of the first joint project being implemented by FAO, IFAD and WFP, and funded by Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation: Mainstreaming Food Loss Reduction Initiatives for Smallholders in Food-Deficit Areas. The CoP provides to registered users an online discussion FORUM, resources (online libraries, databases, repositories with relevant materials), and links to partners. It is a dynamic platform that facilitates information sharing and coordination and is enriched with updated information on a regular basis. The “In Action” section includes projects and legislations and countries where initiatives related to food loss and waste can be searched by term, year, location and category.

Exploitation: The platform was launched in December 2025, and it is under the umbrella of FAO who will probably ensure its sustainability.

3.5. EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste (EU-FLW)

Description: An online platform, in the form of a network, dedicated to food waste prevention bringing together EU institutions, experts from the EU countries, international organisations and relevant stakeholders selected through an open call for applications to better identify, measure, understand and find solutions to deal with food waste.

Governance: European Commission.

Target at: All actors in the food chain interested in solutions for FLW, from farmers, processors, manufacturers and retailers through to consumers themselves. Policy makers, research scientists, food banks and other NGOs also play an important role. Member States have benefited from the exchange of information and experience made possible by the EU-FLW Platform, which have often inspired further action at national level.

Features: The Platform aims to support all actors in defining measures needed to prevent food waste, sharing best practice, and evaluating progress made over time. In addition to plenary meetings, the EU-FLW Platform also operates in sub-groups to examine specific aspects and/or questions related to food waste prevention. Five sub-groups have been established to date: sub-group on Action & implementation, sub-group on Date marking and food waste prevention, sub-group on Food donation, sub-group on Food loss and waste monitoring, sub-group on Consumer food waste prevention. The main objectives of the EU-FLW platform are to: i) set target, measure, monitor and report progress, ii) strength cooperation by sharing, learning and scaling up what was successful iii) made food waste prevention a priority in everyone daily life and habits.

Exploitation: The platform's first mandate was 2016-2021, a second mandate was established in 2022 until 2026.

3.6. Synthesis and critical view

The three European KSPs selected with a general focus on food systems and most discussed nowadays (SFSI, Food2030 online and EU-FarmBook platforms) have each different purposes and governances: one looks to share databases and is governed by many EU funded projects, other looks to build a strong network and other focuses on specific food actors (farmers, foresters and advisors), and these last two are governed by their respective EU funded project. The two Food Losses and Waste dedicated platforms (Technical platform and EU-FLW) are both large platforms, governed by big organisations such EC and FAO. Both features interesting groups and communities, including measuring and monitoring of Food waste.

However, are these 5 platforms known by the food actors? And are they relevant to them? Do they fit their expectations about a KSP?

4. Food actors' expectations

Following the desk study and the analysis of the 5 selected KSPs it is important to understand if whether WASTELESS consortium and other food actors know these KSPs or any others and what expectations do they have from such KSPs. For this purpose, a survey was developed and distributed through WASTELESS website and SoMe channels, partners and networking projects own dissemination channels. It is estimated that the survey reached at least 8000 people.

4.1. Methodology

A Survey entitled “What do you want to find in a KSP?” was published on WASTELESS website through a [newsroom article](#) in November 2023. This [survey](#) is composed of 7 questions (annex I) with a deadline to be filled by March 2024 which was extended in April through Flyers (annex II) distribution. The survey is still running and if reaches a valid statistical number of answers (100) a publication is predicted. The results presented in this deliverable are the ones obtained until May 2024.

4.2. Results and discussion

Within 6 months (Nov 2023-May 2024) 30 people completed the survey, 19 from WASTELESS consortium (63%) and 11 from outside of the project (37%). The countries represented included 9 from MS (Austria, Belgium, Greece, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain) plus Switzerland, Turkey and Canada. The ratio male /female is 0.43 and half of the answers are from the age range 41-60, 37% in the age range of 21-40 and 13% in the age range of 61-80.

Scientific community is the major food chain sector represented (38%) followed by consumers (23%), non-profit associations and/or non-government organisations (18%), food private sector (15%) and finally food retailers and services and policymakers (3%). There are no representatives of funding agencies, food government agencies and private sector from others than food (Figure 1). It is worth monitoring that the food private sector includes food production and/or processing, packaging, advisory & business development and food regulation consultancy. From outside of the WASTELESS project, the contribution came from consumers, scientific community, private sector (food production and/or processing, advisory & business development) and public administration.

Figure 1. Survey participants representation on food chain sectors

More than half of the participants selected all options under “What do you want to find on a KSP?” question (Figure 2). According to the results 70% of the participants want to find sector specific information and knowledge databases and 67% are interested in project related outputs as well as training and education.

One participant outside of WASTELESS project, representing the public administration sector from Portugal wrote the comment “knowledge sharing platforms (KSPs) are very few and sometimes they don't put out results in a concise and practical way”. This comment is interesting as the participant makes a point that few KSPs exist, and their results are not presented in a good way. However, this is in contrast with our findings in the previous sections where we highlight that many KSPs were found. In respect to the way results are presented we cannot express any opinion as this was not the scope of our analysis. Perhaps this can only be understood if the participant is referring to the specific topic of their interest.

Figure 2. Number of answers selected by participants (30) to the question “What do you want to find on a KSP?”

The following question in the survey aimed to find how participants do usually hear about KSPs in general and the answers were diversified, each option was selected by less than half of the participants (Figure 3). The main route of finding these platforms is through projects (47% of participants), followed by search engines, SoMe, conferences, events or workshops selected by 37% of participants and press releases, articles or promotion by colleagues selected by 27% of participants.

Figure 3. Number of answers selected by participants (30) to the question “How do you normally hear about KSPs in general?”

When questioned which KSPs they know, participants identified 23 KSPs listed in Table 2. These KSPs were identified by 19 participants (63%) and some mentioned more than one, 8 participants (27%) answered they

knew none and 3 participants (10%) left the space empty with no answer. Next question asked if they used any KSP and 60% of the participants answered 'no', thus it seems that despite being aware of their existence they do not use them. The participants who answered affirmatively to using KSPs (40%) were further asked to list the KSPs used, and from the 23 KSPs previously identified, only 12 are being used (Table 2).

SFSI platform was the one mentioned by 7 participants probably due to the fact WASTELESS partners already discussed this platform at that point, however only 1 participant uses this platform. Platforms/Websites from different EU projects were mentioned by 3 participants and used by 2, EU-FLW platform was mentioned by 2 participants and used by the 2 and the EU-FarmBook mentioned by 2 participants but used only by 1. Other KSPs were mentioned like association platforms, topic specific platforms, but also repositories and search engines.

Table 2. List of KSPs identified as known by the participants and used or not by them

KSP name	Known by (participants no.)	Used by (participants no.)
Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform	7	1
Platforms/ websites from different EU projects	3	2
EU-FLW Platform	2	2
EU-FarmBook	2	1
Google workspace	2	0
Associação Portuguesa de Nutrição (APN)	1	1
Associations' platforms	1	1
CORDIS	1	1
EIT Food	1	1
EuroFIR platform	1	1
European Sustainable Phosphorous platform	1	1
Slack	1	1
Wikipedia	1	1
ArXiv	1	0
Biorefine Cluster Europe	1	0
Biotechnologia.pl	1	0
EIP-Agri	1	0
European Biogas Association	1	0
Food Engineering KSP	1	0
Food 2030 network	1	0
I2Connect	1	0
Quality and Food safety Management Systems KSP	1	0
Zenodo	1	0

The reasons why the 40% participants use the KSPs are mostly (83%) for research on specific topics, news and events (58%) and collecting data and training opportunities (50%). Less than half of participants, selected the options such as networking, finding databases and curiosity (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Number of answers selected by participants to the question “Why do you use it/them?”

4.3. Synthesis and critical view

The expectations for a KSP of these 30 participants (research on specific topics, news and events, collecting data and training opportunities) is reflected in the purpose of use (find sector specific information, knowledge databases, project related outputs and training and education) of the few ones that are using KSPs. The results show that participants are aware of KSPs existence and could list several, but they do not use them. The reason for not using them should be further explored. Is the content of low quality? Is the content not being presented in an easy, clear and user-friendly way as commented by one participant? Lack of time from participants? Are they difficult to find? The results showed they are being disseminated through diversified channels, but is the dissemination being done in the correct way? Are KSPs not corresponding to their needs?

Solutions to overcome the reasons of not using KSPs should be discussed since it is believed that these platforms are a positive change through free information-networked activities for innovative development.

5. WASTELESS perspective

WASTELESS project aims to reduce FLW with 20% annually by development of tools to measure and monitor FLW. The tools will be tested in different case studies and will be incorporated in a toolbox made available to all interested stakeholders along the food supply chain. For broader dissemination towards a high number of stakeholders the project aimed to develop or become a part of a KSP since its beginning.

D7.1 shows the steps taken towards the decision of creating a WASTELESS KSP or becoming a part of an already existing one, taking into consideration the needs and objectives of the project itself and target groups for dissemination and communication.

The desk study showed that even in a fast search with a broad key word combination, already many KSPs for food systems are available in the form of databases, websites, forums, communities, etc. These KSPs can be further classified in respect to their focus area, main goal and information provided. In the opinion of the authors of this deliverable, there was no justification for creating another KSP, as it would require the use of significant resources and likely result in a lower impact. The WASTELESS project website exists and shares the knowledge produced during the lifetime of the project in different forms. However, there is a need of ensuring that the outputs produced will be available to the users also after the end of the project. Therefore, the path considered was to select an already existing KSP for food systems in line with the needs and objective of the WASTELESS project and target groups.

Further, the existence of so many platforms create confusion and makes the decision of which one to use difficult. Based on currently known platforms focusing of the FLW topic, 5 platforms were selected for an in-depth analysis. The EU-FLW platform, despite its relevance to the FLW topic and governance by the EC, is a large platform where WASTELESS cannot actively participate in its management, thus not meeting the GA requirements. However, this platform is crucial to WASTELESS, as it has already been invited for a brief presentation regarding its aims, pursued impacts, and outcomes. It is expected to begin presenting its outputs in the future. Similarly, the Technical Platform of the Measurement and Reduction of Food Loss and Waste, also within the FLW topic, is a significant platform governed by the FAO. Due to the same reasons as mentioned above, it does not allow compliance with the GA requirements. These two platforms have a high impact as they act under the patronage of big organisations. However, in our opinion, the collaboration with them for communication and dissemination purposes is sometime complicated and slow. EU-FarmBook despite its growing popularity, is dedicated to the real needs of farmers, foresters and advisors, and thus not all the outputs from WASTELESS would be accepted by it. The Food 2030 online platform is governed by a project which will end by 2026 and which aims networking and collaboration, that is out of the scope of a KSP needed for WASTELESS. Nevertheless, WASTELESS is part of this network and participates in meetings and activities they organise. Sustainability of outputs is also an issue as by the time the project ends, the platform will probably end or, in best scenario, will be taken over by others. However, now there was no certainty on this topic. The SFSI Platform covers the needs of the WASTELESS project as it is a knowledge database, with no issues related to sustainability and covers the needs of the target groups of WASTELESS including innovations, case studies, training, etc.

To gain a better understanding of whether the WASTELESS consortium and other food actors are aware of these KSPs or others, and what expectations they have from such platforms, a survey was conducted. The results revealed that food chain actors utilize these platforms to access sector-specific information, knowledge databases, project-related outputs, and training and education resources. The SFSI platform was the most frequently mentioned by survey participants, likely because WASTELESS partners have already discussed this platform in recent months. However, only one participant reported using this platform. Furthermore, the low number of participants in the survey suggests a lack of interest among users in KSPs. It is important to note the limited representation or absence of some key food chain actors among participants (such as funding agencies, government food agencies, and private sector entities outside of the food industry), which may diminish the significance of the results or indicate a lack of interest among these stakeholders in using KSPs.

The options were further discussed with the WP7 partners and the coordinator, and the issue of governance was raised, as the selected KSP should allow the active participation of the project.

All these steps lead to the decision of making WASTELESS a managing project of the SFSI Platform. This ensures the active participation of the project in the future developments of the platform, the reach of a high number of stakeholders acting in the food system and the sustainability of results even after the end of the project.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable shows the steps taken in order to decide whether WASTELESS should create or become a part of a KSP. Based on the desk study analysis, a comparison of 5 well known KSPs and the results of the online survey, the WASTELESS project became a managing project of the SFSI platform as it covers the topic of the project, is in line with the needs of the users and it is governed by several European projects which will ensure sustainability of results even after the end of the project.

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8. Annexes

Annex I – “What do you want to find in a KSP”

WASTELESS - Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress (<https://wastelesseu.com/>) is an EU funded project with the aim to develop tools and recommendations for measuring and monitoring food loss and waste (FLW).

This survey addresses all food actors, including beneficiaries, consumers, and policy-makers, to determine what they want from a Knowledge Sharing Platform (KSP)!

This survey has 7 questions and takes approximately 10 min to complete.

Please consider sharing this survey with anyone who might have an interest in this topic.

All personal information will remain confidential and will not be shared or used beyond the purpose of this survey.

We want to hear from you!

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Other

Age range:

- Under 20
- 21 - 40
- 41 - 60
- 61 - 80
- 81 and over

Job Title:

.....

Country:

.....

1. Are you part of the WASTELESS Project?

- Yes
- No

2. What is/are your PRIMARY role in the food chain?

- policymakers
- government food agencies
- funding agencies
- non-profit/non-governmental organisations/associations
- private sector food production and/or processing, packaging
- food retail and/or service (HoReCa)
- private sector non food
- scientific community
- consumer
- Other: please specify

KSP INFORMATION**1. What do you want to find on a KSP?**

- Sector specific news & events
- Training and education
- Networking possibilities
- Project- related outputs
- Sector specific information and knowledge databases
- Latest findings in a specific topic
- Other (Please specify)

2. How do you normally hear about KSPs in general?

- Via a press release or article
- At a conference/event/workshop
- Via Social Media
- Search engines (Google, Bing, etc.)
- Promotion by colleagues
- As partner in different projects
- Other (Please specify):

3. Which KSP(s) do you know?

.....

4. Do you use any?

- Yes. Which one? (Please specify):
- No

5. Why do you use it/them? (Only if yes at Q4)

- Research on specific topics
- Training opportunities
- Contacts for networking
- Collecting data
- Finding databases
- News and events
- Uploading content
- Curiosity
- Other (please specify)

Annex II - KSP survey Flyer

**What would you like to find on a
Knowledge Sharing Platform?**

